

Survey on the Use of Personas Among VR Professionals

1. Do you have work experience in the traditional software industry (non-VR)?*

- Yes
- No

2. In traditional software projects (e.g., websites, mobile apps), have you used personas? *

- Yes
- No

3. Are you currently working in the VR industry, or have you had VR project experience in the past 24 months?*

- Yes
- No

4. Your primary role. *

- Product Manager
- UX/UI Designer
- VR Developer (Unity or Unreal Engine)
- 2D/3D Content Creator
- User Researcher
- Tester / QA
- Other: _____ *

5. Main VR application domains you work on. *

- Games / Entertainment
- Social VR
- Education & Training
- Industrial applications
- Healthcare applications
- Enterprise applications
- Culture & Tourism
- Marketing
- Other: _____ *

6. Total years of traditional software professional experience. *

- 0–1 year
- 2–3 years
- 4–6 years
- 7–10 years
- 10 years

7. Years working in VR-related roles. *

- Less than 1 year
- 1–2 years
- 3–5 years
- 5 years

8. Current VR company/team size.*

- Startup-stage
- Small
- Medium
- Large

9. What types of personas have you used in VR projects? *

- Based on interviews / fieldwork
- Based on surveys / data clustering
- Market-based personas
- GenAI persona / data driven
- Other: _____*

10. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements about personas in VR projects. Scale: 1 = Strongly disagree, 7 = Strongly agree.*

	2	3	4	5	6	7
I tend to engage in direct prototyping without using personas during the design process.	<input type="radio"/>					
The development cycles and delivery practices in VR projects limit the effective use of personas.	<input type="radio"/>					
Personas are useful for identifying and defining the needs of special user groups (e.g., users with disabilities).	<input type="radio"/>					
Personas have difficulty representing the diversity of users in VR contexts.	<input type="radio"/>					
It is difficult to translate persona-based requirements into concrete design features.	<input type="radio"/>					
The use of fictional personas can negatively impact project outcomes.	<input type="radio"/>					
Personas provide insufficient guidance for designing complex interactions.	<input type="radio"/>					
It is difficult to use personas to inform concrete design decisions.	<input type="radio"/>					

11. In which stages of a VR project are you more likely to use personas?*

- Concept / project initiation
- Requirements definition
- Interaction & UI design

- Accessibility design
- Testing & iteration
- Delivery & training
- Other: _____ *

12. Please describe a specific example where using personas in a VR project succeeded or failed. What happened, and why? If you do not have an example, please describe any similar approach you used that is comparable to personas. *

13. Compared with traditional software, what do you think is the best way to 'understand users' in VR, and why? *

14. In your opinion, how should personas be used to better support activities related to understanding and defining user needs? *

15. If you were to use personas in VR projects, what problem would you most want them to help solve? *
